

HUMANISTIC INSIGHTS AND ETHICAL REFLECTIONS IN THE DIARY OF A YOUNG GIRL

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Abstract

Values are essential beliefs shared by human beings which distinguish good deeds from the deeds which are not considered good, thereby giving meaning to life. Human Values are deeply embedded in our conscious that we do not even know that they even existed. Every human being is guided by a set of core values which constitutes their intrinsic foundation.

In 1942, with the Nazis occupying Holland, 13-year-old Anne Frank and her Jewish family went into hiding in the "secret annex" of an old office building. While living there, Anne recorded her experiences in a diary. By turns thoughtful, moving, and amusing, her account offers a fascinating commentary on human courage and a compelling self-portrait of an extraordinary young woman whose life was tragically cut short. Discovered in the attic in which she spent the last years of her life, Anne Frank's remarkable diary has become a world classic. It is a powerful reminder of the horrors of war. It is an eloquent testament to the human spirit and the Human Values ingrained in the Diary are a good source of learning to the readers of all ages, young and old.

Key Words: *Young Girl, World War II, Jews, Courage, Human Values*

THE VALUES

Values are essential beliefs shared by human beings which distinguish good deeds from the deeds which are not considered good, thereby giving meaning to life. Human Values are so deeply embedded in our conscious that we do not even know that they even existed. Every human being is guided by a

set of core values which constitutes their intrinsic foundation.

Values have a wide array of meaning attached to it. It can range from the psychological beliefs in virtues like hard work, honesty and punctuality, to sociological attributes of self-reliance, harmony of purpose, concern for others etc. We have many real-life

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examples of famous people amongst us who gained success by standing strong by their values. History bears testimony of many such cases where value alone made all the difference. Gautam Buddha on basis of his values of non-violence led the world to emerge as a better place. Ashoka and Akbar, the great emperors marked their ways down the history as legends by ruling the country on basis of their values for equality, justice and impartiality among people. In recent times Steve Jobs, the pioneer of new age technology, brought a world-wide revolution by holding fast to his values of following one's passions and dreams and never losing hope.

Values in Indian Context

Every society has a value system which is a set of consistent values required for ethical integrity of the society. A well-developed value system forms a moral code which can be held either by a single individual or many. The foundation of every value system lies on a principal value on which other values rely. A.N. Tripathi (2009) has categorized the values of a good life as Material values, Societal values, Psychological values, Aesthetic values, Ethical values, Spiritual values and Human values.

The above categorization of the values, however, may not be infallible. They have been considered by many scientists and have not been found comprehensive. Local researches in many countries even added that the list has many pivotal values missing. G.P. Sherry & R.P. Verma (1998) have identified a comprehensive set of values consisting of Religious Values, Social Values, Democratic Values, Aesthetic Values, Economic Values, Knowledge Values, Hedonistic Values, Power Values, Family Prestige Values and Health Values.

Values Crises in Contemporary Indian Society

Indian values and culture which withstood many past upheavals successfully are facing newer challenges today. It may be a very difficult task to examine the nature of value crises in the current environment, yet we cannot escape from it. We have to understand it well. This all-pervasive crisis has many inter-connected dimensions that must be deciphered first to identify its main features so that we could analyse these.

The present value crisis was mainly neglecting other life values like the Aesthetic, Moral and Spiritual values and giving excessive importance to material values of life. Pawan Varma (1998) has stated that for all the achievements of India during the last fifty years, there

is, for its middle and elite classes, a crippling ideological barrenness that threatens to convert our nation into vastly insensitive and unethical aggregate of desires and wants.

The psychological need for belongingness is served by the emotional attachment with which we identify ourselves with our society. It generates a sense of pride in the geography, history, traditions, culture and the heritage of the society. The feeling of belongingness also motivates one to strive for removal of social injustice. The lack of social cohesiveness and social consciousness were therefore the primary features of the contemporary value crises at the societal level.

The value climate of a society is closely linked to the behaviour of its leaders of intellect, like writers, academicians and philosophers. They do so by critical examinations of social situations and generating new solutions to the existing problems. However, the contemporary intellectuals appear to have forgotten their role as no such evidence is visible since independence. Their intellectual efforts and temper had been mainly reactive and critical, rather than proactive and creative.

The contemporary value crisis in the Indian society may be termed best as a cultural crisis. From the time immemorial, Indians had been calling their culture by the name of *Manava Sanskriti or Manava Dharma* (Human culture). We have observed that external image of India in the West often tends to highlight the difference real or imagined between India and the West. Western writers usually miss major aspects of Indian culture and traditions. Even in our country, there were various ways of looking at our own culture. One set of people look at Indian culture with a strong sense of pride and belongingness in it. They draw an emotional response satisfying a psychological need for a cultural identity.

The conflict between tradition and modernity is a recurring theme in the cultural value crisis. As commonly conceived, modernity was an abandonment of tradition, a complete break from it. In the Indian social context, it was popularly seen as flouting of traditions and customs, decrying the spiritual and adopting Western lifestyles glorifying the materialistic view of life. Even at the intellectual level, sometimes consciously but quite often unconsciously, modernisation is taken to mean Westernization.

Influence of Age on Values

Age has its influence over values. The age-factor influence changes in values at various stages in life. A child may have different values which might not remain same when he becomes an adult. For instance, Knowledge Value of a child might change into Power

Value when he becomes adult. Values also change with change in physical strength and memory. Knowledge value and stimulation might degenerate with loss of memory in old age. Children while growing up will have different values than when they become matured. Since most of the values are formed during childhood and adolescence, Value education is needed to improve the value temper of the modern educated Indians so that India develops into a happy and prosperous nation, and a world leader.

The home environment is considered as one of the determinants of academic achievement. Motivation and an academically favourable home environment are likely to enhance the child's motivation to achieve academic success. It is common experience that parents and family's involvement has a significant positive impact throughout the education of children and later on their achievements in life. Parental involvement arises from parental values and educational aspirations and that these were exhibited continuously through parental enthusiasm and positive parenting style. This has its impact on the students' self-perception as a learner and on their motivation, self-esteem and educational aspirations.

As Kar (1996) had put it crisply that the education was not only imparting information or training of skills, it has to give the educated a proper sense of values. The most important strategy for combating the present value crisis would be a comprehensive scheme of imparting value education right at primary and secondary school levels. It may be helpful if scholars are encouraged to mine deep into the popular texts, short stories, novels and narratives, and bring forth the values ingrained there in.

THE DIARY OF ANNE FRANK

Anne's diary begins on her thirteenth birthday, June 12, 1942, and ends shortly after her fifteenth. The diary written over a two years period, talks about her life while she and her family were hiding in Holland. They were staying in the secret attic of the office building where Mr. Frank used to work in order to escape from the Nazis during World War II. During their stay in annex, they were supported by several people in the office building, who risked their own lives to ensure the secrecy of the Jewish hideout and to provide them with food and basic supplies.

Anne's diary covers the daily routine of the occupants of the attic. It also describes in detail the characters of her father, mother, and sister, as well as other occupants consisting of three members of Vans Dans family and one Mr. Dussel, who share the attic with them. Anne's difficult situation is made more complicated by her own adolescence. Her maturing

process, coupled with the misery of her cramped quarters and her constant fear of discovery and capture is clearly seen in the page of the diary. She tells of the conflicts she has with her mother and sister, the support she receives from her father, the love that develops between her and Peter Van Dans, the constant bickering of the inhabitants of the attic, and the deprivations that she must endure while in hiding. She also gives detailed account of what is occurring in the war, especially in Holland, and reflects upon her past life. Unfortunately, her diary is left unfinished, for she, her family and the other occupants of the annex are discovered by the Gestapo and sent to a concentration camp.

The straightforward and simple diary is filled with conflicting emotions, ranging from depression and despair to cheerfulness and pleasure. Anne constantly tries to see the good side of things and have hope in spite of the misery and fear she faces on a daily basis. She even tells of some humorous incidents that occur within the annex. When the air raids and bombing come closer to the office building, however, it is harder for her to be positive, but she tries her best to rally her courage and a zest for living. The second half of her Diary is a testament to the indestructible human will to persevere and survive in the most adverse of the circumstances, where a good number of lessons in human values are ingrained. This paper is aimed at mining out these lessons.

VALUES INGRAINED IN THE NARRATIVE

Courage

Courage has been defined as the ability to control fear in a situation that may be dangerous or unpleasant. While recording the events of 11 April 1944, Anne Frank, the brave and courageous girl states that **you have to have the courage to be yourself**. She said “I know what I want, I have a goal, an opinion, I have a religion and love. Let me be myself and then I am satisfied. I know that I’m a woman, a woman with inward strength and plenty of courage.” In her narration of 6 June 1944, Anne Frank says “Where there’s hope, there’s life. It fills us with fresh courage and makes us strong again.” She goes on further and says, “I can shake off everything as I write; my sorrows disappear, my courage is reborn.” Connecting courage and faith, she says

“Those who have courage and faith shall never perish in misery.”

Positive Thinking

Her recording of 15 July 1944 highlights the value of Positive Thinking. It is optimistic attitude, a practice of focusing on the good in any given situation which can have a

big impact on your physical and mental health. That doesn't mean you ignore reality or make light of problems but she tells you that you should **never give up on yourself and never give up on your dreams**. She said, "In difficult times like what it is at present ideals, dreams and cherished hopes rise within us, only to be crushed by grim reality. It's a wonder I haven't abandoned all my ideals, they seem so absurd and impractical. Yet I cling to them because I still believe, in spite of everything, that people are truly good at heart."

In her narration of 15 July 1944, Anne Frank says "I simply can't build up my hopes on a foundation consisting of confusion, misery, and death. I see the world gradually being turned into a wilderness, I hear the ever-approaching thunder, which will destroy us too, I can feel the sufferings of millions and yet, if I look up into the heavens, I think that it will all come right, that this cruelty too will end, and that peace and tranquillity will return again."

In her writeup of 23 February 1944, suggesting to the readers to think of all the beauty still left around and be happy, she says "I don't think of all the misery, but of the beauty that still remains. As long as this exists, this sunshine and this cloudless sky, and as long as I can enjoy it, how can I be sad?"

Introspection

As we understand, introspection is defined as self-examination, analyzing yourself, looking at your own personality and actions, and considering your own motivations and is considered as an excellent value. In one of the narrations, Anne Frank has displayed clearly the value which can be described as introspection. Contemplating her own thoughts, feelings and sensations, she says "Everyone has inside of him a piece of good news. The good news is that you don't know how great you can be! How much you can love! What you can accomplish! And what your potential is!" She adds further "When you are on your bed at night just analyze all the happenings you had gone through whole day and learn from your mistakes, you will be a better person then. How noble and good everyone could be if, every evening before falling asleep, they were to recall to their minds the events of the whole day and consider exactly what has been good and bad. Then without realizing it, you try to improve yourself at the start of each new day."

Gandhian Thought

It is quite surprising that as a girl of 14, thought process of Anne Frank appears to have influence of Mahatma Gandhi. In her writeup of 27 February 1943, describing Gandhi ji as the champion of Indian freedom, has mentioned about his going on fast; she followed up

the story up to 4 March 1943 when he broke the fast. May be, it is Gandhi effect when she says “Human greatness does not lie in wealth or power, but in character and goodness. People are just people, and all people have faults and shortcomings, but all of us are born with a basic goodness.” She adds “In the long run, the sharpest weapon of all is a kind and gentle spirit.”

Going ahead further, she says “How wonderful it is that nobody need wait a single moment before starting to improve the world. No one has ever become poor by giving, and **whoever is happy will make others happy.**”

Spirituality

In her narration of 6 July 1944, the young girl says, “People who have a religion should be glad, for not everyone has the gift of believing in heavenly things.” On 23 February 1944, she says “The best remedy for those who are afraid, lonely or unhappy is to go outside, somewhere where they can be quite alone with the heavens, nature and God. Because only then does one feel that all is as it should be and that God wishes to see people happy, amidst the simple beauty of nature. As long as this exists, and it certainly always will, I know that then there will always be comfort for every sorrow, whatever the circumstances may be. And I firmly believe that nature brings solace in all troubles and look at how a single candle can both defy and define the darkness.”

The theme of Unity in Diversity is also reflected in the diary of Anne Frank. She says “**We are all different, yet we are all the same.** We all live with the objective of being happy; our lives are all different and yet the same.” Like a philosopher, in her writeup of 1 August 1944, she says “Whoever is happy will make others happy.”

Knowledge Value

Knowledge has been defined as a familiarity or awareness, of someone or something, such as facts (descriptive knowledge), skills (procedural knowledge), or objects (acquaintance knowledge) contributing to one’s understanding and the term can refer to a theoretical or practical understanding of a subject. Knowledge is clearly valuable in the sense of securing success in practical life, or at least making success more likely. Moreover, they normally do not dispute the claim that knowledge is, in some ways, more valuable than other, lesser things, such as mere true belief. But this is where agreement usually ends.

Anne Frank giving due importance to the subject of Knowledge Value suggests that one should be like a little child and never stop questioning. She says “Ever since I

was a little girl and could barely talk, the word ‘why’ has lived and grown along with me. It’s a well-known fact that children ask questions about anything and everything, since almost everything is new to them. That is especially true of me, and not just as a child. Even when I was older, I couldn’t stop asking questions. I have to admit that it can be annoying sometimes, but I comfort myself with the thought that “You won’t know until you ask,” though by now I’ve asked so much that they ought to have made me a professor. When I got older, I noticed that not all questions can be asked and that many whys can never be answered. As a result, I tried to work things out for myself by mulling over my own questions. And I came to the important discovery that questions which you either can’t or shouldn’t ask in public, or questions which you can’t put into words, can easily be solved in your own head. So, the word ‘why’ not only taught me to ask, but also to think. And thinking has never hurt anyone. On the contrary, it does us all a world of good.”

Women Empowerment

Women's empowerment is generally defined as promoting women's sense of self-worth, their ability to determine their own choices, and their right to influence social change for themselves and others. In her narration of 6 July 1944, Anne Frank says, “Women should be respected as well! Generally speaking, men are held in great esteem in all parts of the world, so why

shouldn’t women have their share? Soldiers and war heroes are honoured and commemorated, explorers are granted immortal fame, martyrs are revered, but how many people look upon women too as soldiers? Women, who struggle and suffer pain to ensure the continuation of the human race, make much tougher and more courageous soldiers than all those big-mouthed freedom-fighting heroes put together!” **Societal Values**

In her writeup of 6 July 1944, the young girl says that writing in a diary is a really strange experience for someone like me. Not only because I’ve never written anything before, but also because it seems to me that later on neither I nor anyone else will be interested in the musings of a thirteen-year-old school girl. She says, “Parents can only give good advice or put them on the right paths, but the final forming of a person’s character lies in their own hands.” She is assertive when she says “People can tell you to keep quite on a subject but that doesn’t stop you from having your own opinion. There’s only one rule you need to remember: laugh at everything and forget everybody else! It sounds egotistical, but it’s actually the only cure for those suffering from self-pity.”

When someone at home wanted to know her reaction on a dress that she got on her fourteenth birthday, she said that the memories were worth a lot more than material things. Earning happiness to her meant doing good and working, not speculating and being lazy. She said “Laziness may look inviting, but only work gives you true satisfaction.” In her many writings in the diary, she has displayed a consistent level of maturity. On one occasion she said, “Anyhow, I’ve learned one thing now. You only really get to know people when you’ve had a jolly good row with them. Then and then only can you judge their true characters!”

Conclusion

The Diary of a Young Girl definitely establishes that Anne Frank was not an accidental author or a casual teenage chronicler. She was a writer of prodigious talent and ambition. This paper recommends strengthening of our existing educational ecosystem so that our students, professionals and general readers while studying the literature should continue digging deep for the Values enshrined in therein. Instilling values in the children is crucial to a well-rounded education, and education is not only about producing well-filled minds, it is also about well-formed minds. Value education based academic dynamism is sorely needed for improving the value temper of the modern educated Indians so that India develops into a happy and prosperous nation based upon Vinoba’s appeal of *Antyodaya* (welfare up to the last man) and Gandhi’s universal principle of *Sarvodaya* (worldwide uplift).

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